

Towards cooperation? Reflections on spatial narratives and imaginaries regarding interrelations between small towns and metropolitan cores

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Abstract

The article explores the local perspective of small towns in metropolitan regions by examining place-based narratives in the case study area, the Main-Kinzig district in the Rhein-Main metropolitan region. The research is based on interviews conducted with representatives of small-town municipal administrations. It is argued that place-based narratives and metropolitan imaginaries shape small-town realities and impact regional and local planning decisions and hence can promote or prevent metropolitan cooperation. A comprehensive critical narrative analysis reveals an ambivalent picture of the region and its small towns. Proximity to the bigger cities and good connectivity to the metropolitan region through the central infrastructure corridor seem decisive characteristics of the small towns. However, the narrative of a small and manageable rural municipality also appears powerful. This leads to a planning attitude that can be described as “sailing along in the shadow of the metropolitan region”. Making these implicit narratives and imaginaries explicit open up new potentials for metropolitan understanding and future planning cooperation.

Keywords

small towns,
metropolitan cores,
metropolitan region,
place-based
narratives, spatial
imaginaries, regional
interrelations,
cooperation

Small towns and metropolitan cores – a complex interrelation

Past decades have seen something of a fixation on large cities, while small towns as objects of research have long been neglected (Hannemann, 2005; Porsche et al., 2021; Gribat, 2022; Bell & Jayne, 2009; Bański, 2022). Reflections on metropolitan regions consequently tend to adopt the perspective of the large city. Additionally, when attention has turned to small towns, the focus has frequently been on rural and often peripheral areas (Gribat, 2022). In contrast, small towns in central locations and in growing contexts have received less consideration (Hannemann, 2005; Gribat, 2022; BBSR, 2019).

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Nevertheless, in recent years a growing interest in central small towns has been observed in various disciplines and research contexts. This momentum is often accompanied by a changed research perspective that focuses on small towns and at the same time tries to develop broader understandings by studying everyday “ordinary” places (Mayer & Lazzeroni, 2022).

Here the focus is on (economic) development potentials and local policies (Kaufmann & Meili, 2019; Servillo et al., 2017), socio-economic linkages (Sýkora & Muliček, 2017) or how the general interplay of small towns in urban regions is manifested (Cardoso et al., 2019; Meijers & Burger, 2022). However, there are still gaps in the literature regarding the self-perception and positioning of small towns within the metropolitan region due to implicit assumptions and attitudes (for exceptions see Lorentzen & van Heur, 2012 and Görmer, this issue).

The approach employed in this article aims to introduce an additional perspective on the metropolitan region by focusing on the small-town perspective. Small towns¹ are in a dynamic exchange with their surrounding regions. They are interwoven with each other, shaped by a common history and regional socio-cultural characteristics and they are embedded in a particular landscape that has evolved over centuries. In metropolitan areas, interrelationships between small towns and nearby cities are particularly close due to their geographical proximity and the density of infrastructure. Central small towns,² referring to settlements in spatial proximity to a metropolitan core (BBSR, 2022), are often characterised by intensive commuter relations due to good transport connections, affordable housing and proximity to an attractive cultural landscape that offers opportunities for leisure activities (BBSR, 2019). In addition to these locational advantages, however, the metropolitan landscape frequently accommodates essential infrastructures for transport, energy and water as well as major commercial and logistic areas, leading to increased emissions and potentially exacerbating competition for land use (Bolik et al., 2022). Furthermore, small towns on the fringe of growing metropolitan cores are affected by growth pressures like increasing demand for residential and commercial space in an already tight land market (BBSR, 2019). Urban and regional planning has to deal with these complex interrelations. The analysis of place-based narratives from and about small towns and metropolitan cores may broaden our understanding of implicit assumptions and can provide additional insights about the region and its development potential.

¹ BBSR (2021): According to the ongoing spatial monitoring of the German Federal Institute for Research on Building, Urban Affairs and Spatial Development (BBSR), small towns have between 5,000 and 20,000 inhabitants; this definition is further divided into larger small towns with at least 10,000 inhabitants and smaller small towns with less than 10,000 inhabitants.

² The term “central” comes from the ongoing spatial monitoring of the BBSR. Four types of municipalities are identified: “very central”, “central”, “peripheral” and “very peripheral”. Accordingly, a “central location” describes spatial proximity to a metropolitan core or other major centre and thus represents a counterpart to a “peripheral location”, which in turn is located outside of agglomeration areas (BBSR 2022b). This delimitation methodology is based on a large-scale view, so that there are major differences in terms of the de facto connection of central small towns to nearby centres (BBSR, 2019).

This article examines small-town narratives that refer to the self-perceptions and perceived roles of small towns in the metropolitan region, thus examining local viewpoints, ideas and underlying mindsets. The focus is particularly on the small municipal administrations that nevertheless have to cope with the challenges of the metropolitan region. The approach draws on the concept of the intrinsic logic of cities (*Eigenlogik der Städte*), seeing the city not as representing a general social order or notion of the local, but as a socio-spatial horizon of meaning and action that evokes its own view of the world (Löw, 2018; Barbehön & Münch, 2014; Berking & Frank, 2010; Berking & Löw, 2008).

This article argues that place-based narratives can provide valuable insights into the municipal self-image of central small towns and may help to gain a better understanding of urban and regional planning processes and political decision-making. This investigation thus explores the possibility of shared narratives about a metropolitan region and the small towns within it – made up of a multitude of narratives from small towns. This explorative approach introduces an additional perspective towards small towns in metropolitan regions, one with a number of potentials but also certain limitations. It should be emphasised that the investigation and theoretical positioning is located in the German planning context and accordingly reflects a rather nationally specific planning perspective. Nevertheless, it is certainly possible to draw further conclusions for international small-town research from this specific example. The Kinzig Valley in the Main-Kinzig district of Hesse, Germany is used as a case study for the exploration of narratives, examining the 14 small towns within this research corridor. The study is conducted as part of the joint research project “NaTourHuKi” funded by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) within the funding programme “Stadt-Land-Plus”.³

Tracing the idea of place-based narratives and spatial imaginaries

In the literature, a multitude of definitions try to grasp the broad concept of narratives. Referring to Espinosa et al. (2017), narratives can be described as linguistic sequences through which ideas, metaphors and arguments are related to each other (Keller, 2013). In this article, narratives are therefore not considered as one (literary) genre among many, but as a “principle of generating sense and meaning” (Keller et al., 2020: 36). In this sense, narratives can enable a plausible and coherent reproduction of dynamic relationships and processes, stability and change (Espinosa et al., 2017; Kaplan, 2013). A number of meanings can be summarised in a

³ NaTourHuKi stands for “Sustainable tourism concept for Hanau and the western part of the Main-Kinzig district in the context of the RhineMain Regional Park”. The project aims to develop a sustainable recreation strategy for a spatial corridor along the Kinzig Valley from Hanau to Steinau an der Straße. The participating institutions include three scientific institutions (Technical University of Darmstadt, Heilbronn University of Applied Sciences, Frankfurt University of Applied Sciences) and three partners from praxis (Municipality of Hanau, Regionalpark Ballungsraum RheinMain gGmbH, Spessart Tourismus and Marketing GmbH); <http://www.natourhuki.de>.

narrative so that complex (and conflicting) situations and processes can become comprehensible (Kaplan, 2013; Espinosa et al., 2017). Additionally, by naming the past causes of problems, present responsibilities and future objectives, narratives often organise temporal processes (Roe, 1994; Barbehön & Münch, 2014). Actors can thus experience, understand and interpret their world through narratives (Espinosa et al., 2017).

Various categories of narratives have been discussed in the literature. For instance, Willinger (2022) distinguishes in general between small and grand narratives. Small narratives emerge from social practice and are told by individuals or groups, whereas grand narratives, in the sense of François Lyotard's (1986) meta-narratives, describe continually repeated narratives that evolve over time to become an interpretive pattern through which many people perceive and relate to their environment. A special type of small narratives are design narratives, referring to narratives intentionally developed by experts with a specific planning intention or marketing goal. A different categorisation is undertaken by Somers (1994), who distinguishes between four dimensions: ontological narratives (concerning the identity of the individual), public narratives, meta-narratives and conceptual narratives (i.e., constructions or analytical explanatory models of social science). In her concept, meta-narratives can also be described as "grand narratives" (e.g. capitalism vs. communism) and are therefore usually classified as unspoken and often unconscious basic assumptions (Gadinger et al., 2022). In general, narratives that go beyond the individual and are thus linked to certain cultural constellations can be described as public – for example narratives within a family or an institution (Somers, 1994). These narratives can arise from public discourses as well as being recursively introduced into them (Espinosa et al., 2017). Public narratives are dynamic and open to selective appropriation or reinterpretation by different parties. Isolated individual texts often only contain fragments of more complex narratives. Viehöver (2011: 198–200) sums up public narratives as "usually topic-related narratives, which actors use to define their position".

By collecting the small and public narratives told by representatives of small-town municipal administrations in the Main-Kinzig region, this article looks for commonalities but also underlying regional "world views", mindsets and attitudes. Görmar and Kinossian (2022: 272) use the term "spatial imaginaries" to describe (with reference to Boudreau) "mental maps representing a space to which people relate and with which they identify". Based on this understanding, place-based narratives can be the "political and discursive articulation" of imaginaries, shaping "a place's identity and culture" and being "representations of it" (Paasi, 2013: 1207). Whereas imaginaries are considered intangible and elusive, "operating in the background as abstract world views influencing decision making processes" (Görmar & Kinossian, 2022: 272), place-based narratives are seen as useful entry points to identify them. Therefore, this article focuses, first, on the municipal level by collecting shared narratives of

small-town representatives and, second, on a superordinate regional level by gradually approaching underlying metropolitan imaginaries that can be deduced from the narratives.

Potentials for regional development and metropolitan cooperation

The research perspective on regional interrelations presented above gains further significance if it is assumed that metropolitan imaginaries shape small-town realities and impact regional and local planning decisions, hence promoting or preventing metropolitan cooperation (Davoudi et al., 2018; Valler et al., 2023; Görmar, this issue). Or, to put it slightly differently, narratives as entry points to and manifestations of spatial imaginaries can likewise promote institutional agency (Gadinger et al., 2022) or impede innovation by sustaining the status quo (Markscheffel, 2022). In the German context, these key functions of narratives attain additional importance due to the planning sovereignty of local municipalities guaranteed by German Basic Law (Art. 28 (2) GG). The research approach adopted here can thus help to reveal implicit place-based narratives and spatial imaginaries, thereby opening up new development paths for small towns and regional cooperation. Consideration of place-based narratives and metropolitan imaginaries in planning processes can therefore be valuable for fostering long-term regional development, e.g. when it comes to regional planning.

According to Paul Ricœur, narratives can be understood as birthplaces of possible worlds, as they have a potential for transformation (Espinosa et al., 2017). Görmar and Kinossian (2022: 283) state that “narratives may be ‘pregnant’ with future development options” but in order for these options to be realised “development plans have to fit into a narrative’s frame to avoid social tension, or discontent”. Following these arguments, narratives are only successful if they are embedded in public and everyday communication and can be connected to locally dominant patterns of interpretation (Gadinger et al., 2014; Barbehön & Münch, 2014). Or considering it the other way around, a project can only be successfully legitimised if it is linked to a suitable narrative and thus becomes understandable for the stakeholders concerned (Gadinger et al., 2022). However, spatial narratives are always subjective and biased and to a certain extent unreliable – even if they are presented as facts (Gadinger et al., 2022; Görmar & Kinossian, 2022). But although narratives are “internally complex and contradictory”, they nevertheless “engage in a dialogue with each other” (O’Dowd & Komarova, 2013: 540; see also Görmar & Kinossian, 2022). By analysing the narratives from small towns within a region and extracting metropolitan imaginaries, we trace these dialogues to find out if and how the metropolitan region is evoked and what implications this may have in terms of cooperation and planning. The analysis is structured by the following research questions:

1. What are the collective narratives of the small towns within the case study area?
2. Are there shared metropolitan imaginaries that can be deduced from them?

3. What is the potential value of the discussed perspective in terms of cooperation and regional planning?

Understanding the metropolitan region through the eyes of small towns – the case of the Kinzig Valley

Focusing on the case study area in the Main-Kinzig region, the settlements in a corridor along the River Kinzig from Hanau to Steinau an der Straße were analysed (Figure 1). Next to the regional centre of Hanau (with about 100,000 inhabitants), the research corridor is characterised by an agglomeration of small municipalities (between 3,400 and 23,000 inhabitants), which are located within the Frankfurt-Rhine-Main metropolitan region and in some cases within the Regionalverband FrankfurtRheinMain.⁴ The Frankfurt-Rhine-Main metropolitan region is one of the economically strongest regions in Germany and, indeed, in Europe (Regionalverband FrankfurtRheinMain, 2022).

Of the 19 municipalities in the case study area, 13 municipalities can be classified as “very central” and six as “central” (BBSR, 2022). Besides Hanau, there are two medium-sized cities in the study area and 14 small towns (including six small and eight larger small towns) and two rural municipalities (BBSR, 2021 and footnote 2).

As explained above, this article focuses on small towns. Therefore, the explorative research is focused on the place-based narratives and spatial imaginaries collected or deduced from the 14 small towns in the case study area. The settlements are embedded in agricultural and forest areas, crossed by numerous rivers and streams. Following the topography, the watercourses flow into the Kinzig, which runs from the small town of Steinau an der Straße to its estuary in Hanau, where it unites with the River Main. The Kinzig Valley forms the backbone of the research corridor (Bolik et al., 2022). There is a long history of settlement in these municipalities, which are accordingly characterised by a number of important historical buildings and urban centres. Along the Kinzig River, there are attractive landscape areas with valuable nature reserves that provide habitats for protected animal species such as storks, beavers and kingfishers. However, the valley is also a highly frequented infrastructure corridor. The A66 motorway as well as the Hanau-Fulda regional line and the highspeed rail line (due to be further expanded in the near future) are located in the valley. Additionally,

⁴ The “Regionalverband FrankfurtRheinMain” covers about 2,500 square kilometres and has 2.4 million inhabitants. The zoning was defined in the “Law on the Frankfurt/Rhine-Main Metropolitan Region” (MetropolG) in 2011. The area includes the cities of Frankfurt am Main and Offenbach am Main as well as the cities and municipalities of the districts of Hochtaunuskreis, Main-Taunus-Kreis and Offenbach. The Main-Kinzig district, the Wetterau district and the Groß-Gerau district are represented in the regional association by only some of the municipalities. The “FrankfurtRhineMain metropolitan region” is much broader than the area covered by the “Regionalverband”. It has an area of about 14,800 square kilometres, has about 5.8 million inhabitants and extends over large parts of the three federal states of Hesse, Rhineland-Palatinate and Bavaria. The FrankfurtRhineMain metropolitan region is one of 11 metropolitan regions in Germany defined in 2005 (Regionalverband FrankfurtRheinMain, 2022).

industrial estates and logistic areas protrude into the Kinzig Valley and its floodplains, often blocking the connection between settlements and valley (Bolik et al., 2022).

Figure 1 – Location of the Kinzig Valley, not to scale, I. Bolik, TU Darmstadt

The search for place-based narratives started with semi-structured interviews with representatives of small-town municipalities, carried out via video conference between November 2020 and March 2021.⁵ The explorative nature of the interviews was intended to generate insights into the (subjective) local perspective of small-town administrations and foster approaches for further investigations. It should be noted that the statements of the interviewees, as municipal representatives, may be affected by the desired image and marketing of the small town in question. However, it became apparent in the interviews that the representatives were willing to speak critically about the urban situation and political decisions, so that many personal attitudes were explicitly reflected in the narratives.

⁵ Representatives from 13 of the 14 small towns in the investigated area participated in the interviews. All in all, a total of nine mayors and eight representatives of small-town municipal administrations, e.g. from the main and human resource departments, the building authorities or the areas of tourism and city marketing, took part in the exchanges. The interviewees were selected on the basis of suggestions from the municipal administrations. The interviews therefore focused on the internal perspective of the local administrations and the subjective perspective of the person interviewed. It should also be noted that there was only one woman among the suggested interviewees. Furthermore, all of the interviewees were also citizens of the small central towns examined.

The interviews included questions about the current principles of municipal development, as well as the perceived role of the municipality within the metropolitan region. In addition, the interviewees were asked to characterise their municipality in keywords. Hence, the chosen method offered snapshots into various municipal administrations within the case study area.

Drawing on Görmar and Kinossian's (2022) framework of critical narrative analysis, the case study was researched using three analytic dimensions: first, descriptive analysis of the individual interviews; second, cross-comparison of the entire interview data; and third, recontextualisation of the findings from the interviews. This multidimensional approach was chosen due to its explorative character; in contrast to other approaches to narrative analysis, the researched object is examined from different perspectives (e.g. a specific spatial context). This enables a broad search for narrative fragments and, at the same time, discipline-specific methods, such as explorative mapping, can be included in the research process.

In a first step, the interview data was analysed through a structuring qualitative content analysis (Kuckartz & Rädiker, 2022). The transcribed interviews were structured using deductive (a priori) categories, for example by identifying sections referring to characteristics of the small town or its relationship to the metropolitan region. Further inductive sub-categories were developed from the transcriptions. Here, the focus was on the search for fragments of place-based narratives. For this reason, uninterrupted passages in which the interviewees told their story freely, striking metaphors, ascribed roles and recurring plots (Gadinger et al., 2022) were of particular interest. The process was supported by coding software. To verify the clarity and repeatability of the subjective classification, the categorisation under an already formed code was repeated and thus crosschecked by different persons (Kuckartz & Rädiker, 2022).

Ultimately, the question was whether shared imaginaries of the metropolitan region under investigation can be deduced from the snapshots gained by interviewing several small-town administrative representatives. Hence, the search for recurring and thus collective narratives in a cross-comparison of the individual interviews formed the second dimension of the analysis. This cross-comparison revealed two thematic complexes in which competing and/or shared narrative lines could be identified, as discussed in more detail below.

The objective of the third dimension of the analysis was recontextualisation, which involved the narrative lines identified in the cross-comparison being related to the social, spatial and temporal contexts shaping the investigated area. Further analytical methods, such as statistical data, spatial analyses using geographic information systems (GIS), explorative mapping and fieldwork mapping, were additionally employed in order to relate the interview statements to a larger context. Explorative mapping is a method that uses different combinations and overlays of selected spatial structures (settlements, water and transport structures, topography, forestry and agricultural areas) to gain insights into morphological connections and regional relationships (Corner, 2011).

As the interviews were conducted and transcribed in German there may be some limitations due to the double translation – from oral to written and from German to English (Souto-Manning, 2014). In addition, the verbatim citations of the spontaneous responses have been edited in this article to improve readability, e.g. filler words and duplicates have been deleted. For data protection grounds, the statements of the interviewees have been anonymised and are identified using consecutive letters.

Narrative lines regarding the essence of a “typical” central small town in the Kinzig Valley

During the semi-structured interviews, the municipal representatives were asked to describe their municipalities in keywords. The interviewees often draw an ambivalent picture, on the one hand emphasising separation from the metropolitan region and, on the other hand, highlighting the location of the municipality in the growing metropolitan region. In one interview, a mayor aptly summarises the simultaneity of these two often contradictory narrative poles and at the same time illustrates the effortless reverting to and switching between these lines of narrative.

A: “The answer always varies depending on who is asking, let’s put it that way. Depending on what we want or what we want to represent, it can be viewed in both ways.”

The first of the narrative poles mentioned refers to a conscious demarcation from the neighbouring cities and thus also to a certain distancing from the metropolitan region itself. In the interviews, proximity to nature and the village-like structures of the small towns are repeatedly emphasised and linked to a very positively connoted narrative of rurality. Statements that are representative of this positioning can be found throughout all the interviews, for instance:

B: “We are the municipality in the green countryside. Municipality, that is really a [small] municipality and you can also say almost a village and we are undoubtedly in the countryside – the largest area here is wooded.”

C: “There are now people who are moving from the city to the countryside [meaning small town C] and prefer to drive from there rather than to live in this chaos, in the hustle and bustle every day. Because rents are becoming increasingly unaffordable in the city. So you accept that: you pay less rent, maybe you have to travel for an hour, but then you have peace and quiet again in the evening.”

The location, which is often perceived as rural, combined with other locational advantages such as affordable housing, is described by interviewees as the essential characteristic of small towns in the Kinzig Valley. However, rurality is not connoted as deficient or peripheral, but rather as the main advantage over the cities. The size of the small towns also plays a significant role here and is often linked to a narrative of manageability, family friendliness and village

cohesion. “Lovable and liveable town” is a recurring description, or as one mayor aptly sums it up:

D: “It’s not as anonymous as it is in Hanau, I think that’s another essential character trait. I would almost say that this social cohesion is what makes us special.”

At the same time, this narrative of positive rurality and manageability seems threatened by the neighbouring cities and the growing metropolitan region. Many municipal representatives report on the “pains of growth”. In one interview, this recurring, ambivalent relationship to the metropolitan region and the “urban character” of the neighbouring cities becomes particularly clear:

E: “And then, of course, we also have to deal with growth and pains of growth. We are such a nice little town, and everyone knows everyone, so of course that gets lost [...] You have to be careful when you have an urban character. An urban character does not only have sunny sides. Of course, issues such as crime are also part of it. There are also other issues that are not so exciting, and you have to make sure that your image stays at a high level.”

The interviewees frequently describe the metropolitan region as being overburdening or overwhelming – especially in regard to the tight housing market and demands for new residential building land. This is often linked to the high pressure on social infrastructure caused by new citizens. The demand for new housing seems to conflict with the small towns’ self-image as a rural and thus manageable community. This tension is accurately described by a head of the municipal office in the following statement:

F: “Healthy growth as a rural region! When I look around me, I see where too many buildings have already been constructed: in the municipalities of the Rhine-Main region, which are no longer able to compensate [with nature protection measures to offset designations of new building areas] on their own land – if they build. So, something is going wrong.”

This conflict also becomes clear when the interviewees describe the future development of their small towns. Here it frequently seems necessary to defend the narrative of rurality against a growing or even encroaching metropolitan region, as articulated in the following interview excerpt:

G: “However, we – in our development concept – we have stated that our goal is, for example, to maintain the rural character. Meaning a maximum of approximately up to 10,500 inhabitants. That means a maximum increase of about 600 people. That is what has been set.”

Other municipalities formulate this perceived conflict somewhat less forcibly, with statements such as the following:

H.: “Where we want to go is to keep growing but growing with a sense of proportion. That was a bit difficult in the past – we have designated a lot of building land.

Municipality H. has grown a lot in a comparatively short period of time, which has led many people to say: sorry, but enough is enough. We first have to make sure that we grow together again, because that is actually one of our strengths. We were a sworn community and now the goal must be to integrate the newcomers.”

Manageability and a “everybody-knows-everybody” mentality are presented as important positive characteristics of the small towns in the Kinzig Valley. At the same time, however, some interviewees also mentioned the challenges posed by the large number of small-town districts in their municipality.

I: “I’ll put it this way, the territory of the small town is also very spread out, it goes from to the Vogelsberg to the Spessart. And local public transport is not like in the big city, where you can take the underground or the tram and whiz off to wherever, which is very difficult here if you don’t have a car.”

Most of these settlement structures are the result of territorial reform in Hesse in the 1970s, leading to scattered and fragmented settlement structures (Figure 2). The affiliation of the individual small-town districts and their administrative boundaries cannot be deduced from this map. Some small towns consist of only one historically evolved municipal district. Others consist of a large number that have been combined as a result of the municipal territorial reform. The aim of the reform was to merge small municipalities without full-time administrative staff into larger units and thus improve their administrative power and efficiency (Hessisches Ministerium des Innern, n.d).

Figure 2 – Settlements (left) and administrative boundaries (right), not to scale, I. Bolik, TU Darmstadt

The differences in settlement morphology become particularly clear when comparing the settlement areas and the municipal boundaries (Figure 3). The proportions of settlement area to open space vary greatly. It is also noticeable that the administrative units further away from

the core of the metropolitan region are larger in terms of area and have a greater number of scattered districts. Especially in the case of these municipalities, it is questionable whether they can be described as small towns in the sense of historically evolved towns with certain central and urban functions (Sýkora & Mulíček, 2017). Rather, they appear to be administrative constructs in which the formerly independent villages were combined into new administrative units. Within the case study area, it is therefore advisable to understand the term “small town” from an administrative perspective, i.e. in the sense of a small municipality rather than a small town (Servillo et al., 2017; Bolik et al., 2022).

Figure 3 – Comparison of settlement bodies, I. Bolik, TU Darmstadt

This aspect of the “scattered and spread-out small town” is also taken up in some of the interviews and linked to the challenges posed by people thinking in terms of separate districts, especially the older generations, as well as the search for a community-wide identity, as becomes clear in the following excerpt:

G: “We are a child of the municipal territorial reform, now 51 years old. Yes, it also took these decades and especially among the older people there is still a bit of resentment – the largest district is still referred to as ‘the city dwellers’, who are somehow different, but among the younger people it plays a much less important role.”

While relations between the different small-town districts are sometimes described as difficult, the connection to the neighbouring cities is seen as a significant locational advantage. This narrative repeatedly emerges as a second pillar alongside the one described above. Here, the focus is clearly on the advantages of the metropolitan region, particularly on being “well connected” (both for citizens and businesses) and “well supplied”, which are also described as essential characteristics of the small towns under consideration. One mayor summarises this narrative line as follows:

J: “We are such a ‘near-by’ small town. We are close to the Rhine-Main region. So, we are well connected here in terms of transport. We are well connected in terms of supply, and of course we are also close to nature – in fact we are in the middle of it.”

In general, the interviewees paint a rather positive future narrative for their municipalities, especially because of the growing metropolitan region. Future-oriented, innovative and prosperous are adjectives that come up again and again in this context. The advantages of the good connections through the infrastructure corridor of the Kinzig Valley and the central location within the metropolitan region are clearly in the foreground here (see section 3.3). However, what is not mentioned in this context is also noticeable: the noise and emissions from the infrastructure corridor (car and railway alike) as well as the way in which the valley is cut in two, which will also be intensified in the future by the expansion of the high-speed rail line. When asked about his assessment of the planned expansion of the high-speed rail line, one mayor, for example, gives the following statement:

J: “Yes, there will be a valley-cutting bridge when the long variant four [chosen route for the high-speed train] is built. I see this very calmly. I mean, of course, we are a bit limited in designating new residential areas. But they will sell in the end, too – I know. [...] I have already enquired elsewhere and for many actors and also for me, the world will not collapse. It’s a super popular form of transport. Travelling by train. I can live with it [the bridge]!”

This assessment, alongside similar statements from other interviewees, seems surprising, since at the same time the interviewees repeatedly emphasise tranquillity, closeness to nature and the location “in the countryside” as essential parts of their small-town narrative. To sum up, in their self-portrayal, the interviewees frequently oscillate between the two poles mentioned. On the one hand, there is conscious differentiation from the neighbouring cities, e.g. by emphasising rurality, manageability and closeness to nature. On the other hand, proximity to the bigger cities and good connections to the metropolitan region also seem important characteristics described by the interviewees (Figure 4).

Figure 4 – Summary of narrative lines regarding the essence of a “typical” central small town in the Kinzig Valley, F. Delija, TU Darmstadt

Narrative lines regarding connectedness within the metropolitan region

In order to develop a better understanding of the internal views of the small-town administrations about metropolitan interaction, interviewees were asked about the most important points of orientation for their citizens within the metropolitan region. On the topics of local supply, shopping and leisure activities, no uniform picture emerged from the answers of the individual administrative employees. Rather, a small-scale network of attributed functional relationships between the small and medium-sized towns and cities of the region was described. On the other hand, when the interviewees spoke about the topics of work and business, a clear and very strong focus on the large cities of the Rhine-Main area emerged: Hanau, Offenbach and Frankfurt were repeatedly mentioned in this context. One representative sums up this perceived interaction with the neighbouring cities as follows:

C: “Well, the people work there. They live here [in small town C] and drive there every day. That is the link to the large city. The fact that work is available there for the people. [...] All mobility always goes towards the Rhine-Main [meaning Frankfurt, Offenbach and Hanau].”

In the interviews, the big cities of the Rhine-Main region were usually linked with the keywords commuting and working and contrasted with living in the small towns. Parts of this recurring narrative of working in the “hectic big cities” and living in the “green and quiet” small

town are aptly summarised by a mayor in the following statement with regard to his municipality:

H: “So far it has been like that: work in the Rhine-Main area and live on the edge of the Rhine-Main area and then also enjoy the quality of life here, which is also offered here by the proximity to nature.”

It is also interesting to note that some interview partners describe the functional links with the large cities as being stronger than the relationships between the individual small-town districts of their municipalities. The challenges of the territorial reforms described above and the – in some cases – still difficult search for a municipality-wide identity seem to resonate in these statements (see section 3.2). In addition, the lack of transport links between the districts and, more generally, the lack of reasons for exchange between the small-town districts seem to reinforce this circumstance, as one mayor puts it:

J: “So one example I’ll never forget: a very old birthday guest told me two years ago, from the most southern district X, that he’d never been to the most northern district Y. But that also has to do with transport connections. Yes, or some kind of familial relationships.”

For a better understanding of this context, it is again worthwhile to recontextualise these interview findings with the help of other methods of analysis, such as explorative mapping.

While the municipal affiliations of the individual small-town districts often appear arbitrary, the connections between the morphology of the settlements and the logic of the landscape structure (especially the water network and topography) are clearly discernible. The settlement structures are integrated into an environment that can be read as a cultural landscape of agricultural and pastureland, bordered by forest and woodland areas. The settlements run along the courses of the rivers and their valleys, which flow into the Kinzig Valley. This is even clearer when the presumed locations of the historical town centres are considered (Bolik et al., 2022; see Figure 5).

Historically, the towns were well connected to the Kinzig River and the infrastructure axis of the Kinzig Valley. This corridor can be traced back to the medieval trade and military road *Via Regia*, which connected the trade fair cities of Frankfurt am Main and Leipzig – and which essentially corresponds to the course of the A66 motorway today (EKT, 2021). The transport link between Hanau and Fulda was expanded into the so-called “Kinzigtal Motorway A66” from the 1970s onwards. Economic progress through better connections to the large cities appears occasionally in the interviews as an argument for this expansion of the infrastructure corridor (Bolik et al., 2022). This promise still seems to be shared and carried forward by many municipal representatives today. In the interviews, a focus on the large cities or a connection to them via the infrastructure corridor often appears in connection with the desired or successful establishment of local businesses. Motorway exits and railway stations along the infrastructure corridor are described as key factors for the attractiveness of a business or

industry location. One mayor summarises this central role of the infrastructure corridor for perceived regional interaction as follows:

H: “[We] have ideal conditions due to our locational advantages, which we have with our location on the A66 and with the good connection to Frankfurt’s main railway station – both for businesses and for people looking for a new home.”

Figure 5 – Settlement morphology - landscape structures, not to scale, I. Bolik, TU Darmstadt

At this point, the question arises whether the perceived interaction between the individual small towns and the cities of the Rhine-Main area is not solely linked to spatial proximity, but above all to access to the connecting infrastructure corridor. The interviews provide initial indications of the central importance of the infrastructure corridor for the regional sense of belonging. Further, the impact of the growing metropolitan region on the small towns studied also seems to be linked to access to the infrastructure corridor. Thus, for example, the projected relative population development (for the years 2012-2030), reveals a differentiated picture. While moderate to strong growth is forecast for the municipalities close to the core of the metropolitan region, many municipalities further away show signs of slight to strong shrinkage (Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2020). However, it is not only distance to the metropolitan area that seems decisive for this, but also connections to the infrastructure corridor in the Kinzig Valley (Figure 6).

Population trends 2012–2030 (%)

source: Bertelsmann Stiftung 2020

Growing and shrinking communities
(Authors' classification)

Figure 6 – Growth - connection to infrastructure corridor, not to scale, I. Bolik, TU Darmstadt

Although the interviews could only provide snapshots of the small-town administrations investigated, they nevertheless gave valuable insights into the self-image of small towns within the case study area and revealed something of the perceived interrelations in the metropolitan region (Figure 7). In the last section, the narratives that emerged are therefore briefly summarised and conclusions for regional cooperation and planning examined.

Figure 7 – Summary of narrative lines regarding connectedness within the metropolitan region, F. Delija, TU Darmstadt

Findings and discussion of narrative analysis, underlying spatial imaginaries and their role in planning

This article explores the shared narratives in a metropolitan region and the small towns within it – made up of a multitude of small, public narratives told by representatives of municipal administrations. By examining place-based narratives referring to the self-perception of the small towns and their perceived roles in the metropolitan region, current topics and local viewpoints have been traced. This section summarises the essential findings of the narrative analysis and considers the underlying spatial imaginaries as the attitudes or “worldviews” that can be derived. In brief, spatial imaginaries have been defined as “mental maps representing a space to which people relate and with which they identify” while place-based narratives can be viewed as their “political and discursive articulation” (Görmar & Kinossian, 2022; Paasi, 2013). Finally, attention turns to the potential role and value of the collective narratives of the small towns and shared metropolitan imaginaries for cooperation in urban and regional planning.

In the search for shared narratives, semi-structured interviews were conducted with representatives of small-town municipal administrations within the case study area of Main-Kinzig in the Rhein-Main metropolitan region. After being transcribed, the interviews were examined considering the framework of critical narrative analysis (Görmar & Kinossian, 2022; Fairclough, 1992). The data is subject to some limitations, as the interviews and represented

viewpoints can only be seen as a snapshot of opinions within the municipal administrations. However, the primary aim of the article is not to present comprehensive results of the case study, but to introduce an additional perspective embracing the viewpoint of the small towns towards the metropolitan region and its cores. The analysis of the place-based narratives has identified two thematic complexes with ambivalent narrative poles, which at time compete. The first complex focuses on the internal view and self-perception of the small towns, while the second complex deals with the perspective towards the metropolitan region.

The first ambivalent narrative pole is dominated by a surprisingly positive connotation of rurality, closeness to nature and village structures (“nice little town”, “peace and quiet everyday”), despite the fact that all the municipalities are part of a rapidly growing and very central metropolitan region. Rurality is not connoted as a deficit or even a disconnection, but rather as the decisive advantage over the cities. Thus, this self-image is used to distance the small towns from the metropolitan cores – which are accordingly assigned antonyms like “anonymity”, “chaos” and “hustle and bustle everyday”. At the same time, a narrative of growth and growing pains is told, which is determined by the metropolitan region’s excessive demands, like the increasing pressure on the housing market, new industrial and logistic areas, traffic and social infrastructure. These narratives hint at imaginaries that perceive the familiarity of the community and the easy-to-manage rurality as virtues that need to be protected against the expanding or even encroaching cities. This view seems to be directed inwards, with a focus on growing together to strengthen and improve the common identity. Growth seems to be regarded with concern and therefore should rather be limited, following the mottos “grow with a sense of proportion” or “healthy growth as a rural region”. Some interviewees even call for an end to growth, i.e. an end to the designation of new building areas.

The second narrative pole is characterised by the notions of being “well connected” and “well provided for” within the metropolitan region. A positive image of the future is drawn, with terms such as “future-oriented”, “innovative” and “prosperous” due to the “fortunate location in the metropolitan region”. The good connections are mainly due to the highly frequented infrastructure corridor in the Kinzig Valley (at the same time a valuable natural area with floodplain landscapes and nature conservation areas), which can be seen as the “backbone of the region”. The downside of this good connectivity are emissions, especially noise – which were experienced as highly dominant in fieldwork. Strikingly, this factor does not appear in the narratives. In fact, the Kinzig Valley seems to be a “blind spot” which the small towns turn their backs on, while looking at the adjacent landscapes. The imaginaries behind this refusal to recognise the negative impacts of the transport infrastructure might reveal a deeply grounded conviction that the connections are of crucial importance for the small towns. Even the further expansion of the high speed trainline does not seem to disturb or change this “looking in the other direction”.

The second complex (dealing with the perspective on the metropolitan region) focuses on narratives about connections within the region. There appear to be no linear patterns of connections for local supply and leisure, but rather many small-scale networks spanning the region. However, there is a clear and strong orientation towards the large cities (Frankfurt, Hanau and Offenbach) in the case of labour relations. Here again, the narrative of working in the hectic big cities and living in the green and quiet small town is told. It is interesting that some of the perceived linkages to the cities seem to be stronger than those between the individual small towns themselves. Indeed, many small towns can be seen rather as administrative constructs consisting of formerly independent villages than as coherent towns with distinct central functions. This situation resulted from the administrative reform of the 1970s, but also from the historical interplay of landscape structures and settlement morphologies. The infrastructure corridor, as an ancient trade route, is part of this logic as well. Prosperity and growth seem to be strongly dependent on connections to the infrastructure corridor – which is possibly even more important than spatial proximity to the metropolitan cores.

Nevertheless, in many places large commercial areas lie like buffers between the small towns and the Kinzig Valley, so that the connection to and perceptions of the valley are disturbed. A certain risk accrues from this as the imaginaries largely seem to perceive the Kinzig Valley as a kind of “disposal mass” for traffic and commerce and to forget about the valuable natural space with its great potential for local recreation. At the same time, however, the interviews also provide indications of the central importance of the corridor for the regional sense of belonging. Thus, the revitalisation of this “backbone of the region” could be an advantageous planning approach.

To conclude, the interviewees repeatedly emphasise the benefits of an economically strong metropolitan region, but without wanting to give up or even question their own narratives of small, manageable, and rural municipalities (in distinction to the large cities). In the majority of the interviewed municipalities, this complacent attitude is also underlined by a lack of independent urban development concepts, although these actually represent an important element of German municipal planning sovereignty. With reference to the concept of borrowing and shadowing, these ambivalent imaginaries could also be described as “sailing along in the shadow of the metropolitan region”. Or as Meijers and Burger (2022: 32) put it: “It may be quite comfortable in the shade when trying to escape the heat”. Although external factors (such as connectivity or spatial context) certainly have a great influence on municipal development, case studies show that small towns can impact their own (economic) municipal development, especially through land-use strategies and regional coordination (Kaufmann & Meili, 2019). In the face of multiple crises (climate crisis, housing crises, energy crisis, etc.) it therefore seems questionable whether these rather passive and comfortable imaginaries are still sustainable.

The joint research project NaTourHuKi (the framework for the narrative analysis presented here) pursues the objective of establishing a cooperation structure with actors in the region and aims to initiate a planning process. In this context, the argument that planning can only be successfully legitimised if it is linked to locally dominant narratives and is thus rendered understandable for the stakeholders (Gadinger et al., 2022) is particularly interesting. The narratives discussed here provide a particular insight into the administrations of small towns, touching on current issues and on the imaginaries behind them. With regard to (inter-municipal) coordination and regional planning, these findings can offer valuable starting points for making implicit assumptions explicit, discussing them with municipal actors and thereby possibly opening up new development paths for metropolitan cooperation.

However, it should be emphasised that the narrative analysis was only one element among other methodologies (like mapping, statistics and fieldwork) in the toolbox. Moreover, only the narratives of one stakeholder group, the representatives of the municipal administrations, have been explored. Further stakeholder groups in the region, like local citizens, representatives of nature conservation groups, agriculture etc. have also been involved and activated using different participation formats such as workshops, surveys and city walks. Nonetheless, the narrative analysis contributed greatly to the overarching objective of drawing a comprehensive kaleidoscope-like picture of the metropolitan region and of the interrelations between small towns and metropolitan cores.

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Conflict of interest

The author declares no conflict of interest.

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